

Consumers Awareness and Sustained Moral Consumption in Buying Ready-Made Clothes in Saudi Society

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Abstract

This study deals with moral and sustained buying of ready-made clothes in Saudi Society. It aims to study the expenditures on buying clothes by consumers under study. Besides, it aims to show how to get rid of clothes, focusing on social and environmental awareness on one hand, and on motives of sustained moral consumption on the other hand. This is represented in a random sample of (700) consumers from the society, to which the method of social survey is applied. A questionnaire is written as an instrument for data collection, such as the sample's members, and analyze this questionnaire by using statistical tests. The study conclusions show that there is a strong relationship between the financial level and motives for buying. It also shows that people with high-incomes tend to spend on buying clothes. The study agrees with many studies that have dealt with this aspect, and its conclusions also show that the most important reasons for disposing of clothes are due to the change of size, and the end of their consuming age, which indicates their awareness of the importance of responsible and sustained discarding of clothes. The study also recommends the increase of awareness of sustained consumption and the importance of recycling, in addition to improving communication channels between consumers and Charity Societies.

Keywords: consumer's behavior, ready-made clothes, moral consumption, sustained fashion, consumers,

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1. Introduction

People's consumption behavior has a great impact on the overexploitation of the earth's natural resources (Dermody et al., 2015). The most important impacts are consumers' strong desire to have clothes continuously and discard them quickly, which will have a devastating impact on Earth, and a clear change in the climate. This is explained by the International State Organization concerned with climate change, that human activities contributed to the greenhouse emissions and the phenomenon of global warming (IPCC, 2023). Fashion industry is classified as one of the largest global environmental pollutants (Lascity & Cairns, 2020), as fashion industry has gone through a rapid growth that led to the increase of consumption, and the change in the consumers' behavior (Ishaq & Tawfiq, 2022). One of key challenges at present time is how to change consumers, behavior to a more sustained consumption. This, in turn, contributes, to a great extent, to the solution of the environmental crisis as regards the pollution created by the fashion industry, and the reduction of the negative impact of over consumption, or what is called 'Consumerism' (Dermody et al., 2015). It also contributes to reducing the use of natural resources to the minimum level and the use of poisonous materials, emissions of garbage and pollutants on the life cycle. This will contribute to the preservation of future generations' needs (Contribution of Working Groups I, 2023). Council (2016.02.22) defines sustained consumption as the use of products and services with ways that reduce environmental impacts and in a way that meets human needs at present and future generations.

Both Harris et al. (2016) and Dermody et al. (2015) highlight the challenges that consumers face in adopting sustainable consumption behaviors. These challenges can be classified into internal and external barriers. Internal barriers include limited awareness and understanding of sustainable practices, as well as a lack of personal motivation to engage in sustainable fashion choices. External barriers, on the other hand, are primarily related to the limited accessibility and availability of sustainable products in the market. The study of Thanaa and Khadigjah (2012) mentions the most important internal and external factors affecting the individual in the Saudi society regarding clothes consumption, and the culture of purchase consumption. The study reached the idea that behind every purchasing behavior of consumption is a fulfillment of human needs and desires, which they may differ from one person to another according to their goals and the types of their characters as well as their purchasing potentials. Al-Zahrani (2017) observed that, despite rising income levels among Saudi families, a prevailing pattern of frequent clothing purchases persists—indicative of a consumerist mindset that disregards both genuine need and the environmental consequences of overconsumption. Moreover, Al-Dabbagh (2008) indicates that the purchasing power is one of the most important factors affecting the consumerist behavior of the Saudi Women in buying clothes. She explains that the income level directly affects the quality and quantity of clothes that a Saudi woman buys. Women of high income tend to buy luxurious brands, while other women prefer to buy more economical clothing. The present study problem is represented in the effect of the economic factor (the quantity of expenditure) on buying ready-made clothing, and the reasons that drive the consumer to discard them, in addition to the extent of the consumer's awareness of the moral sustained consumption in the Saudi society, which is the aim of this study.

2. The Literary Presentation

Purchasing Consumption of Clothing

Developments contributed to finding out serious desires towards consumption. It is not confined to developed countries or developing ones, or poor families or rich families. On the contrary, consumption becomes a common behavior for all categories and classes of society (Al-Ramani, 2010, p. 13). Besides, rapid changes in social and economic conditions, the tremendous progress in industrial technology, and the plentiful and inexpensive of raw materials help change the world into a consumer market (Ishaq & Tawfiq, 2022). Considering that the consumer is the driving force of all industries, The fashion industry has undergone rapid transformation, particularly with the widespread rise of fast fashion, which stands as one of the major barriers to ethical and sustainable consumption. This phenomenon has become globally prevalent, especially in industrialized and capitalist economies, attracting consumers from diverse social and economic backgrounds. As a result, it has contributed to a noticeable decline in consumer moral awareness and a weakened commitment to sustainable development goals. (Barnes & Lea-Greenwood, 2006). perspective, utilizing data from 4,617 adult participants across Germany, Poland, Sweden, and the United States. Their analysis identified five distinct consumer segments characterized by differing purchasing behaviors. The results indicated that individuals with lower incomes predominantly purchased low-cost clothing from budget brands, whereas a smaller, higher-income segment favored mid-range to luxury labels. Notably, a subgroup composed mainly of women exhibited a relatively high purchasing frequency, particularly for affordable fashion items. The study also stated that there is a small category of high income consume medium-ranged trademarks to expensive ones. Between these two categories, there is a women category that buys at a higher rate than a medium one of limited-price trademarks. The study of Thanana and Khadijah (2012) concludes that clothing consumption behavior of individuals in the Saudi society is influenced by several internal and external factors. The internal factors include personal factors. They are: needs, desires, values and personal beliefs that affect the choices of clothing. "Psychological factors also play an important role in defining the consumer behavior of clothing" (Sharma, 2021). As for the external factors, they include social and cultural factors that affect the choices of clothing such as customs and traditions and social inclinations. Besides, the economic factors play a vital role in defining the clothing consumption behavior such as income and price. As for the culture of purchasing clothing behavior in the Saudi society, it is affected by values and beliefs. The previous study agrees with the study of Ishaq and Tawfiq (2022) in that the social, psychological and social motives affect consumerism of fast fashion in the Saudi society. Several key factors were under focus, among which are: psychological and social factors such as: The desire for social distinction, belonging to a particular group, and the role of emotions, feelings of self-satisfaction.

Sustained Moral Consumption

Moral consumption indicates the practices that take into consideration the environmental, social, and economic impact on the length of the whole life cycle of a product (Govind et al., 2019). It is also referred to by responsible consumption, which means that the individual's decisions in his consumption behavior have an impact on environment and society (Thøgersen & Ölander, 2006). The change in the consumer's behavior is attributed to environmental issues such as climate change, global warming, threats affecting biological diversity (biodiversity), ecological systems, and natural resources, in addition to its impact on public health (Dermody et al., 2018). This shift in awareness has given rise to a distinct

category of consumers known as moral consumers—individuals who deliberately limit their consumption and make purchasing decisions guided by ethical principles (Shaw & Newholm, 2002). Such moral consumption encompasses both conscious and sustainable approaches, where choices are shaped by concern for societal and environmental well-being. Conscious consumption is an individual reaction that focuses on achieving personal satisfaction by acquiring and using products and services that have a positive impact on social, economic and environmental relationships (Jackson, 2004). As for sustainable consumption, it is the result of group work among effective entities in the society. Accordingly, it is an extension of conscious consumption (Kingston, 2021). Research show that the individuals tend to develop moral and environmental purchasing behaviors when they believe that their actions could help mitigate environmental problems (Park & Lin, 2020). The study of Bairrada et al. (2024) addresses the impact of moral values on the consumer's purchasing intentions in Peru and Portugal, where data are gathered from 520 people, and show positive results indicating no bias in the methods used.

Consumers' Awareness and its Impact on the Environment

Awareness is defined by Blackmore (2016) as: One's direct realization of himself and the environment surrounding him. It is pertinent to the manner in which something is, or the work is done. Technological advancement, globalization, and changes in consumer purchasing behavior have led to the emergence of a new method of production called fast fashion. Thus, the latest trends of fashion become available for consumers in large numbers and reduced prices. This has resulted in many negative effects on the environment and society, and the labor in charge of manufacturing, as well as the consumer (Hasan, 2017). The increasing heaps of clothing wastes have become an environmental issue (Paço et al., 2021). One of key environmental issues is the pollution resulted from the fashion industry as an outcome of using energy and unrenewable resources for fiber production, and the consumption of large quantities of water and agricultural lands, in addition to the emissions of chemical materials from air and water (Blackburn, 2009). Besides, the burial of textile waste has brought about another problem pertaining to the issue of decomposition. (Žurga et al., 2015), Joyner Armstrong et al. (2016) state that there is an increasing attention of consumers to environmental care, such as redesigning, reducing the use of natural resources, improving the product's quality and lifespan. However, this environmental interest is not reflected in the consumer's adoption of effective behavior and decision. As a result, there remains a noticeable gap between the values consumers express and their actual buying habits. Despite consumers stated concern for sustainability, affordability often outweighs environmental considerations in their fashion purchasing decisions. (Joergens, 2006). Harris et al. (2016) mentions that even among green consumers, their purchases of clothing are determined based on their personal and economic abilities. Discarding clothing is driven by acquired routine habits. Conscious consumption means reducing, recycling, and reusing of all that is possible for the protection of the environment (Paço et al., 2021).

In this study, the researcher seeks to direct those interested in the communities, especially Arab communities, to the protection of environment and its unrenewable resources, especially in the fashion industry, by their sustainability, and launching awareness campaigns to consumers of clothing the aim of which is increasing the consumers sector who are interested and aware of moral principles regarding clothing consumption, in addition to the fact that what is manufactured and marketed is eco-friendly.

Based on what is mentioned earlier, the study aims to examine the motives affecting the consumer in the spending processes on clothing purchasing, which represent; the economic factor and the motives for discarding clothing. It also aims to raise consumers' awareness in the Saudi society by the moral and sustainable consumption of clothing.

As discussed above, two hypotheses for the study arise. They are:

- There are statistically significant differences that exist between the average spending scores of the sample individuals on clothing purchases based on the study variables, which are: (amount of spending – purchase periods – types of clothing most purchased – the most purchasing age group).
- Statistically significant differences exist between the average scores of the sample individuals on the consumers' awareness of moral and sustainable consumption of clothing and their impact on the environment and society in accordance with the study variables, which are:
 - To support the recycling of clothes to benefit from them.
 - To boost the collection of clothing wastes by specialized organizations to benefit from them.
 - To communicate with Charity Societies when discarding clothes.

3. The Methodology

The Method

The method of a social survey is adopted to verify the validity of the study hypotheses.

The Sampling

It is a human sample: a random sample consisting of (700) consumers in Saudi Arabia. The questionnaire is distributed by using 'Google Form' for ease and speed of the publication among consumers. Distribution began from February to July for six months in 2024. Twenty-eight (28) questionnaires were removed for non-completion of data filling.

Instruments

To build a closed-ended questionnaire which is used as a tool for data collection consisting of two main axes and seven subordinate phrases.

- *The first axis* includes financial expenditure on buying clothes. It comprises four subordinate phrases. They are: Amount of expenditure – Buying periods – The most purchased types of clothing – The most purchasing age group.
- *The second axis* includes the consumers' awareness of the moral sustainable consumption of clothing regarding the environment and society. This comprises three subordinate phrases, which are: Boosting the recycling of clothes to benefit from them – Supporting the collection of clothing wastes by specialized organizations to benefit from them – Communicating with Charity Societies when discarding clothes.

Validity of the Survey

- Calculation of the internal consistency validity of the questionnaire using Pearson Correlation Coefficient between the score of each item consisting of each axis, and the total score of the axis (the dimension) in the questionnaire.
- **First Axis:** Spending on buying clothes:

Table 1 demonstrates that all correlation coefficients are significant at the level of 0.05 – 0.01, which indicates the validity and homogeneity of the questionnaire phrases.

- **Table 1**
- *Values of the Correlation Coefficients Between the Scores of Each Item (phrase) and the First Axis.*

No.	Correlation	Significance
1-	0.752	0.01
2-	0.614	0.05
3-	0.818	0.01
4-	0.903	0.01

- **Second Axis:** Consumers' awareness of the moral and sustainable awareness of clothing and its impact on the environment and society:

Table 2 illustrates that all correlation coefficients are significant at the 0.05 – 0.01 levels. This indicates the validity and homogeneity of the questionnaire's phrases.

- **Table 2**
- *Correlation Coefficient Values Between the Scores of Each Item and the Third Axis*

No.	Correlation	Significance
1-	0.623	0.05
2-	0.764	0.01
3-	0.915	0.01

- The validity of the questionnaire was assessed through internal homogeneity by calculating Pearson correlation coefficients between the total score of each axis and the overall score of the questionnaire, titled "The social awareness of sustainable, moral consumption in purchasing ready-made clothing in Saudi Arabia."

Table 3 shows that all correlation coefficients are significant at the 0.01 level, indicating the validity and consistency of the questionnaire axes.

Table 3

The values of Correlation Coefficients Between the Total Score of Each Axis and the Total Score of the Questionnaire

Axes	Correlation	Significance
Axis One: Spending on buying clothes	0.735	0.01
Axis Two: Consumer awareness of sustained moral consumption of clothing and its impact on the environment and society	0.797	0.01

Reliability of the Questionnaire

Reliability was calculated using Cronbach's Alpha, the split-half method, the Spearman–Brown correction formula, and Guttman's method.

Table 4 demonstrates that all values of the reliability coefficients (Alpha coefficient, split-half, Spearman–Brown, and Guttman) are significant at 0.01 level, indicating the stability of the questionnaire.

Table 4

Values of the Stability Coefficient for the Dimensions of Social Awareness of Sustainable Moral Consumption in Ready-Made Clothing Purchases in Saudi Arabia

Axes	Cronbach's Alpha	The split-half method	Spearman Brown	Guttman
Axis One: Spending on buying clothes	0.917	0.888	0.948	0.902
Axis Two: Consumers' awareness of sustainability and moral awareness of clothing and its impact on the environment and society	0.754	0.720	0.789	0.749
Stability of the questionnaire coefficient for the dimensions of social awareness of sustainable moral consumption in ready-made clothing purchases in Saudi Arabia.	0.862	0.834	0.892	0.850

4. Results and Discussion

Based on existing literature, the results of several studies assert that the fashion industry relies on enormous and continuous production of low-priced clothing. Subsequently, this helped consumers spend on buying clothes continuously and discard old ones. Many studies assert consumers' increasing interest in protecting the environment and sustainable consumption. To study this in Saudi society, the researcher distributed a self-questionnaire among a random sample of clothing consumers in Saudi Arabia for data analysis and employed statistical tests. "Analysis of Variance" and the "Scheffé test" were used to determine the direction of significance and verify differences among sample members for multiple comparisons. Additionally, a t-test was used to achieve the study's objectives.

To test the first hypothesis, which suggests statistically significant differences in the average spending scores of the sample individuals on clothing purchases based on the study variables, an Analysis of Variance was conducted and Scheffé test was applied. Tables 5 and 6 display the spending processes on clothing purchases. The results demonstrate that the Saudi consumers' spending on clothing purchases and following of fashion trends are high. This corresponds with many studies that show a strong relationship between the material level and motives for clothing consumption in societies. Additionally, some studies assert that high-income individuals spend more on clothing purchases and following fashion (Fitzmaurice & Comegys, 2006; Joy et al., 2012; Lascity & Cairns, 2020). Furthermore, the emergence of fast fashion has contributed to increased spending because their prices are within the consumer's reach. In contrast, Jalil and Shaharuddin (2019) emphasizes that spending among Malaysians is moderate, which indicates consumer awareness.

Tables 7 and 8 illustrate the purchasing periods. This indicates consumer awareness, though the spending process is high. The results corresponds with the study by Thanaa and Khadijah (2012) that consumption in Saudi society is governed by psychological and sociological motives.

Moreover, Tables 9 and 10 demonstrate that the consumption of underwear and work outdoor clothing explains the high expenditure on the purchase of such clothing. Frequent washing of underwear helps to shorten their usable life; moreover, purchasing of work/outdoor clothing highlights the psychological and social motives that drive consumer purchasing and ongoing expenditure.

Tables 11 and 12 clarify that the highest age group are those who are young adults. This is associated with the previous statement, as it is the age group that engages in

employment and social activities, which encourages spending on buying clothes. For the consumer, it fulfils the wish for social distinction and belonging to a particular group, in addition to the role of emotions and feelings of self-satisfaction. This has been emphasized by Ishaq and Tawfiq (2022).

Table 5*Analysis of Variance of Sample Individuals' Spending on Clothing Purchases*

The amount spent on purchasing clothing	Total of squares	Mean of squares	of Freedom scores	F value	Significance
Between groups	24066.447	12033.223	2	56.156	0.01
Inside groups	149353.793	214.281	697		
Total	173420.240		699		

Table 5 clarifies that the F-value was 56.156, which is statistically significant at the level of 0.01. This finding indicates the presence of significant differences among the sample individuals regarding spending on clothing purchases. To identify the direction of significance, the

Table 6*Scheffé Test for Multiple Comparisons*

The amount spent on purchasing clothing	100SR and less m=8.637	500SR and less m=12.644	1000SR and less m=18.526
100SR and less	-		
500SR and less	4.007**	-	
1000SR and less	9.889**	5.882**	-

Table 6 clearly indicates that there are statistically significant differences at the 0.01 level regarding spending on clothing purchases within Saudi society.

Table 7*Analysis of Variance in the Scores of the Sample Individuals at Times of Clothing Purchases*

Time of clothing purchases	Total of squares	Mean of squares	of Freedom scores	F value	significance
Between groups	24534.858	8178.286	3	44.555	0.01
Inside groups	127754.223	183.555	696		
Total	152289.081		699		

Table 7 illustrates that the F-value is 44.555, which is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. To identify the direction of significance, the Scheffé test for multiple comparisons is applied. This finding is displayed in Table 8.

Table 8*Scheffé Test for Multiple Comparisons*

Time for clothing purchases	Monthly m=6.523	From 3-6 months m=15.444	When needed m=19.615	Events m=10.384
Monthly	-			
From 3-6 months	8.921**	-		
When needed	13.092**	4.171**	-	
Events	3.861**	5.060**	9.231**	-

As Table 8 shows, there are statistically significant differences at the 0.01 level at times of clothing purchases.

Table 9

Analysis of Variance in the Scores of the Sample Individuals Regarding the Most Consumed Types of Clothing

The most consumed types of clothing	Total of squares	Mean of squares	Freedom scores	F value	Significance
Between groups	25230.953	5046.191	5	34.313	0.01
Inside groups	102061.789	147.063	694		
Total	127292.742		699		

Table 9 confirms the F-value is 34.313, which is a statistically significant value at the level of 0.01. To identify the direction of significance, the Scheffé test is applied for multiple comparisons. These findings are illustrated in Table 10.

Table 10

Scheffé Test for Multiple Comparisons

Most purchased clothing type	Children's clothes m=9.327	Men's clothing m=4.114	Women's clothing m=12.598	Underwear m=19.367	Going out and work clothing m=16.063	Sleep and loungewear m=6.192
Children's clothes	-					
Men's clothing	5.213**	-				
Women's clothing	3.271**	8.484**	-			
Underwear	10.040**	15.253**	6.769**	-		
Going out and work clothing	6.736**	11.949**	3.465**	3.304**	-	
Sleep and loungewear	3.135**	2.078*	6.406**	13.175**	9.871**	-

Table 10 confirms the existence of statistically significant differences at a 0.01 level.

Table 11

Analysis of Variance in the Scores of the Sample Individuals in the Age Group with the Highest Clothing Consumption in the Family

Age group with the highest clothing consumption in the family	Total of squares	Mean of squares	Freedom scores	(F) Value	Significance
Between groups	23734.397	7911.466	3	32.999	0.01
Inside groups	166863.972	239.747	696		
Total	190598.369		699		

Table 11 clearly shows that the value of F is 32.999, which is statistically significant at the level of 0.01. To identify the direction of significance, the Scheffé test for multiple comparisons is applied. The following Table illustrates those findings

Table 12*Scheffé Test for Multiple Comparisons*

Age group with the highest clothing consumption	From the cradle to early childhood m=9.354	From the middle to late childhood m=14.222	From youth to maturity m=17.293	From maturity to old age m=5.703
From the cradle to early childhood	-	-	-	-
From middle to late childhood	4.868**	-	-	-
From youth to maturity	7.939**	3.071**	-	-
From maturity to old age	3.651**	8.519**	11.590**	-

Table 12 reveals statistically significant differences at the 0.01 level in the age group with the highest clothing consumption.

The Second Hypothesis

There are statistically significant differences between mean scores of the sample individuals regarding the consumers' awareness of the sustained moral consumption of clothing on the environment and society according to the study variances.

The t-test and analysis of variance were conducted on the scores of the sample individuals to verify this hypothesis. Table 13 illustrates these findings.

From the results of Table 13, the study sample supports the recycling of clothing and benefits from this by achieving sustainability. The study agrees with the findings of Shaw and Newholm (2002).

Table 13*Differences in the Mean Scores of the Sample Individuals in Supporting the Recycling of Clothing to Benefit from Them*

Supporting the recycling of clothing to benefit from them	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Sample	Freedom scores	Value (t)	Significance
Yes	18.532	2.123	597	698	7.778	Significance at 0.01 in favor of "yes"
No	10.572	1.597	103			

Table 13 indicates that the t-value was 7.778, which is a statistically significant value at the 0.01 level.

Moreover, Table 14 clearly indicates the participants' awareness of the importance of donating to charity organizations to benefit from old or unwanted items. The findings of this research are consistent with the conclusions of Bin Hamdan (2023), who emphasized the role

of charitable organizations in collecting and recycling used clothing as a means to promote sustainability and mitigate environmental harm. The current study also demonstrates that participants generally find it accessible to engage with such organizations, reflecting a level of consumer awareness regarding the environmental and social benefits of donating clothes to those in need. Accordingly, Saudi society has a moderate sustained moral awareness. The findings agree with those of Al-Zahrani (2017) which reveals an accepted level of awareness of the concept of sustained consumption in Saudi society. However, there is still a need to improve this awareness and conduct more studies.

Table 14

Differences in the Mean Scores of the Sample Individuals in Supporting the Collection of Waste Clothing by Specialized Organizations to Benefit from Them

Support of clothing waste collection by specialized organizations to benefit from them	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Sample	Freedom scores	Value (t)	Significance
Yes	19.227	2.087	674	698	13.934	Significance at 0.01 in favor of "yes"
No	5.947	1.333	26			

Table 14 shows that the t-value was 13.934, which is a statistically significant value at the 0.01 level in favor of "yes." The mean score for the "yes" group was 19.227, whereas the mean score for the "no" group was 5.947.

Table 15

Analysis of Variance in Scores of the Sample Individuals in Communicating with Charities when Discarding Clothing

Communicating with charities when discarding clothing	Total squares	of Mean squares	of Freedom scores	F Value	Significance
Between groups	23609.363	11804.681	2	47.302	0.01
Inside groups	173944.221	249.561	697		
Total	197553.584		699		

Table 15 illustrates that the F-value was 47.302, which is a value of statistical significance at the 0.01 level. To identify the direction of significance, the Scheffé test for multiple comparisons was applied. The following Table clarifies this result.

Table 16

Scheffé Test for Multiple Comparisons

Communicating with charity organizations when discarding clothing	No contact with them m=7.290	Difficult to contact m=11.258	Easy to contact m=16.333
No contact with them	-		
Difficult to contact	3.968**	-	
Easy to contact	9.043**	5.075**	-

Table 16 clearly reveals that there are statistically significant differences at the 0.01 level.

5. Conclusion

The fashion industry is considered as one of the largest industries globally. Fast fashion has created a consumers' market that drives spending to cope with fashion trends. This constant pursuit creates a persistent desire in consumers to dispose of old clothing to obtain new items, without considering the environmental impact and clothing life cycle. This further contributes to exploiting available resources for the continuation of industry and consumption, which will create a cycle of adverse results concerning environmental protection and sustainability. Therefore, consumers should be more responsible with their purchasing decisions. Additionally, there should be a development of awareness toward moral consumption; if this is created in the consumer's mind toward what is bought and consumed, sustainability is realized. This, in turn, is expected to guide the fashion industry toward ethically driven and socially responsible production. Thus, the world's goal of protecting the environment and its resources is realized; the responsibility of achieving sustained moral consumption should not be placed only on the consumer. This creates a cyclical process, where fast fashion leads to more consumption and ultimately, to environmental pollution. Raising consumer awareness fosters an ethically driven fashion industry, contributing to the reduction of environmental pollution.

6. Limitations

This study has some limitations:

- **First** That restrict its generalized findings to the study sample, as it was applied to a random sample within Saudi society.
- **Second** The study does not address the effect of psychological and social factors on moral consumption and sustainability.
- **Third** The study was conducted on consumers within Saudi society, which will enable its application on consumers in other societies and contribute a useful addition to existing literature.

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